

Determinants of Customer Satisfaction in Shopping Malls

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Abstract

Shopping malls represent a modern trend in shopping. Mall culture is considered a significant transformation in the life style pattern of Indians, as shopping has evolved from merely purchasing products to a status symbol and one-stop retail solution. The shopping malls are increasing to keep up with the consumers changing needs. Customers are being influenced by many factors that lure them into having a shopping experience at different malls. Understanding the determinants of customer satisfaction is vital for shopping mall owners to identify customer preferences and accordingly plan their mall offerings. This study seeks to identify the main factors influencing customer satisfaction in shopping malls and evaluate satisfaction levels across different mall attributes in Mangaluru city. A sample of 400 mall customers from Mangaluru were chosen through convenient sampling technique for data collection. Reliability was assessed, Fisher's Exact Test or Chi Square test along with the Friedman's test were employed to examine the relationships and test the hypotheses. The study findings show that, attributes like facilities, promotional strategies, pricing strategies, process, location, reliability and additional services hold an important role in forming customer experiences, attract more customer traffic and provide maximum satisfaction to the customers in shopping malls. This has resulted in repeated purchase, loyalty, customer retention and profitability to the shopping malls. The insights from this study will allow mall owners to better serve new generations of customers and offer unique shopping experiences in order to sustain in this competitive market.

Keywords: *retailing, shopping malls, customer experience, customer satisfaction.*

JEL Classification codes: *M31, M37.*

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Introduction

The rapid growth of retail industry has resulted in rise of shopping malls throughout India. Shopping malls represent a trend in shopping with a facility where consumers can shop for wide range of products all at one end and also avail entertainment facilities like movie theaters, gaming etc. Shopping malls have become very popular and for most of the families, a visit to the shopping mall is like a day outing. Earlier customers used to visit malls often to purchase various products and services but now, when budding buyers visit malls, they are looking for outstanding experiences that go well beyond conventional shopping. Consumers' expect for product alternatives, buying convenience, discounts, offers etc. Thus, mall owners must know their target customers to provide

an experience that makes their visit worthwhile. The threat of E-Commerce has influenced the shopping malls to rearrange themselves as recreation hubs. However, by differentiating the consumer offerings with innovative add-ons and experiences, shopping malls can deliver a level of entertainment and leisure that cannot be satisfied in online shopping. Customers are being influenced by many factors that lure them into having a shopping experience at the shopping malls. Factors such as mall ambience, products, price and promotional strategies, service quality, facilities provided and location has an influence on the purchasing decision and satisfaction of customers. Customers differ to a large extent in their satisfaction and are unpredictable while selecting a retail shop and products which must be studied and analyzed. Customer satisfaction in today's world is the distinguishing element between success and failure. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze factors which bring about customer satisfaction based on which improvements and shopping experience can be planned. Understanding the level of customer satisfaction is essential for a mall because satisfied customers are likely happy, loyal and use the full range of facilities and services provided by shopping malls. As malls continue to grow, particularly in Tier 2 and Tier 3 cities, they are becoming essential platforms for local businesses to scale and for promoting sustainable and experiential retail practices thus use an extensive range of facilities and services offered by shopping malls.

Review of Literature

Anselmsson (2006), identified eight essential factors of the shopping malls that influence customer satisfaction includes selection, atmosphere, convenience, sales people, refreshments, location, promotional activities and merchandising policy. El-Adly (2007), analyzed six mall appealing factors from the shoppers' perspective, namely comfort, entertainment, diversity, mall essence, convenience, and luxury. Kim, Lee, & Gu Suh (2015), studied the consumers' reaction to the marketing initiatives adopted by a shopping malls involves sensory, emotional, perceptual, and behavioral aspects. Study highlights that the overall shopping mall experience significantly impacts customer satisfaction, fostering loyalty and enhancing brand personality. Although the mall personality affects satisfaction, it does not directly impact loyalty. Ubeja & Bedia (2012), states that customers often perceive shopping as a fun and recreational activity with little awareness of ongoing sales promotion while shopping in malls. Customers expect variety with quality and good services. Banerjee (2012), indicates that the image of a mall is one of the most important attractiveness dimension for consumers. Stores in malls must offer a diverse range of international brands, quality products at reasonable prices, provide exceptional service delivery through well behaved and mannered staff, and keep a constant supply of stocks. The additional aspects that enhance mall attractiveness are providing proper rest areas, dedicated play corners for children, movie theatres, and restaurant, stores with popular brands and high quality merchandises, entertainment options, sophisticated ambience with modern architectural design, facilities that ensure adequate security for consumers are crucial to make customer feel safe and valued. Jhamb & Kiran (2012), focused that consumers prefer organized retail formats due to significant product related features such as improved quality, wide variety of brands, assortment of merchandise. Additionally, store attributes like convenient parking facility, trained sales personnel and comprehensive security further enhance the shopping experience. The retention activities, promotional activities, growth and improvement initiatives, pricing strategies and competitive approaches are the key drivers of the growth of organized retailing and play a vital role in boosting the sales. Madan & Kumari (2012), examined the increasing awareness and brand consciousness across various socio-economic classes in India, which has contributed to the development urban and semi-urban retail markets. It emphasizes that adequate parking facilities and overall service quality are essential in enhancing customer satisfaction.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out using primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through the structured questionnaire from the customers of City Centre Mall and Forum Mall of Mangaluru city. Considering the monthly average footfall, a sample of 400 respondents were selected as the respondents from the 2 malls of Mangaluru city. The respondents for the study were selected using a convenient sampling technique. Reliability was assessed, Fisher's Exact Test or Chi Square test along with the Friedman's test were employed to examine the relationships and test the hypotheses. Secondary data were collected by referring to various journals, web sources, previous research articles, and were incorporated wherever necessary to support the primary data.

Results

From the below table it is evident that the alpha reliability coefficient is greater than or equal to 0.8. Therefore the data collected by the researcher is considered reliable and used for various statistical analysis.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient Value

Mall Dimensions	Total Number of Respondents(n=400)
Location	0.795
Ambience	0.915
Product	0.900
Price	0.786
Promotion Strategies	0.915
Additional Services	0.911
Various facilities	0.926
Process	0.875
Reliability	0.830
Staff Members	0.884
Community Development services of the mall	0.907
Customer Care Service	0.772
Promotion of corporate social responsibility	0.806
Customers Satisfaction	0.819
Problems faced while shopping	0.784
Factors for improvement	0.871
Overall	0.980

Source: Primary data.

Table 2. The Various Demographic Factors Calculated Fisher's Exact Test Value or Chi Square Test Value and Their Significance for the Respondents

Customer satisfaction	Chi square test Value (CSTV) & Fisher's Exact Test Value (FETV) and significant value (p value)	
Gender	FETV=3.591	P=0.107>0.05(NS)
Age	FETV=13.764	P=0.087>0.05(NS)
Marital status	CSTV=4.734	P=0.107>0.05(NS)
Education qualification	FETV=37.148**	P=0.000< 0.01 (S)
Occupation	FETV=14.805	P=0.089>0.05(NS)
Monthly Income	FETV=21,289**	P=0.000< 0.01 (S)
Family Composition	CSTV=4.361	P=0.170>0.05(NS)

Association with malls	FETV=25.162**	P=0.000 < 0.01 (S)
* Significant at 5% l.o.s	** Significant at 1% l.o.s	

Source: Primary data.

H1: There is no association between customer satisfaction from the shopping malls and demographic variables of the respondents.

From Fishers Exact test t is observed that the demographic variables such as education, monthly income, association with the malls have a significant impact on the customer satisfaction at 1% level of significance as the p values are less than 0.01 but with the variables like age, gender, family composition, marital status of the customers and occupation has no impact on satisfaction of the customers of Mangaluru city. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected for all of the factors except for age, gender, family composition, marital status and occupation of the customers.

Table 3. Test Results of Mean Ranking for the Customer Satisfaction towards Various Dimensions of Shopping Malls

Satisfaction - Ranks	Mean Rank	Rank	
Location	7.08	5	Friedman's Test value = 446.823 d.f=12 p value = 0.000 < 0.01.000 < 0.01
Ambience	6.61	12	
Product	6.46	13	
Pricing strategies	7.27	3	
promotional strategies	7.46	2	
additional services	6.96	7	
Facilities	7.55	1	
Process	7.12	4	
Reliability	7.06	6	
staff behavior	6.77	11	
community development program	6.90	8	
customer care service	6.85	10	
promoting corporate social responsibility	6.89	9	

Source: Primary data.

H2: There is no significant difference in the mean ranking for the customer satisfaction towards various dimensions of shopping malls.

The calculated Chi square value is 446.823 with a significance level of 0.000 for 12 degrees of freedom is which less than 0.01. Therefore it is confirmed that there is a significant difference in the mean ranking between the variables. From the above table it can be inferred that compared to other indicators “facilities” with mean rank 7.55 is a very important factor in terms of satisfaction by the customers. “Promotional strategies” with mean rank 7.46 is having a significant effect on satisfaction by the customers next to facilities. “Pricing strategies” (7.27) and process (7.12) are having significant impact on the satisfaction by the customers of Mangaluru city. The most influential factors in comparison to others were tested with Friedman test. Since asymptotic significance (sig.) is less than 0.01 (1% level of significance), the hypothesis is rejected. This supports the alternative hypothesis that there is significant difference in the mean ranking for the satisfaction by the customers of Mangaluru city. This indicates that, in Mangaluru city the customer satisfaction was more due to attributes like facilities, promotional strategies, pricing strategies, process, location, reliability and additional services than the other factors like community

development programme, customer care service, corporate social responsibility, staff behaviour, ambience, and products offered in shopping malls.

Figure 1. Radar Chart Showing Customer Satisfaction
Source: Primary data.

Discussion

The shopping style of customers of Mangaluru has completely changed. Earlier people avoided single complex fearing the lack of choice, premium pricing and a class division, which today has become a pleasant experience due to the introduction of shopping malls. Everyone wants to be a part of this innovative stylish experience. The rapid increase in the disposable income and spending patterns of customers of Mangaluru reveal that there is progress in the economy of the city. Customer satisfaction aids in refining the features of products and services.

The results of Fisher’s Exact Test indicate that certain demographic factors significantly influence customer satisfaction in malls within Mangaluru city. Specifically, educational qualification, monthly income, and association with malls exhibit a significant impact on customer satisfaction at the 1% level of significance ($p < 0.01$). This recommends that these factors significantly influence customer experiences and perceptions. On the other hand, age, gender, family composition, marital status, and occupation do not show a statistically significant relationship with customer satisfaction. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected for educational qualification, monthly income, and association with malls. These insights highlight the significance of financial and behavioural variables in influencing customer satisfaction, whereas basic demographic characteristics may have a limited role in this context.

The results of the Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 446.823$, $df = 12$, $p < 0.01$) show a significant difference in the mean ranking of various drivers affecting customer satisfaction in shopping malls within Mangaluru city. The Friedman test further approves that some factors exert a stronger influence on customer satisfaction compared to others. Among the examined indicators, “facilities” appears as the most crucial element of customer satisfaction. This is followed by “promotional strategies”, “pricing strategies”, and “process”, all of which significantly impact customer satisfaction. These findings suggest that infrastructure, marketing efforts, pricing approaches, and operational processes play a crucial role in shaping customer experiences in malls. Additionally, other

contributing factors such as location, reliability, and additional services also enhance customer satisfaction, whereas aspects like community development programs, customer care services, corporate social responsibility initiatives, staff behaviour, ambience, and the variety of products offered appear to have a relatively lesser influence. Since, the null hypothesis is rejected, it confirms that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean ranking of satisfaction indicators. These insights highlight the significant drivers of customer satisfaction in shopping malls of Mangaluru, highlighting the need for mall owners to focus more on facilities, promotions, pricing, and service processes to boost overall customer experience.

The retail business is presently under a significant transformation, where retailers integrating digital tools such as E-Commerce, Social Media, and M-Commerce into their offerings. This shift presents both opportunities and challenges for retailers, mall owners, and society as a whole. A potential direction for future research is to explore the influence of digital media on both virtual and physical shopping experiences of customers, examining how these technologies shape consumer behaviour and preferences. Additionally, with the growing importance of rural markets, malls are becoming more accessible and approachable. Further studies could focus on the evolving role of malls in rural retail marketing, evaluating their influence on consumer engagement and economic development in these areas.

Conclusion

Customer satisfaction is a crucial point of differentiation and to attract new customers in a competitive business atmosphere. Customer satisfaction has revealed the expectation and experience that the customer had with the product and services offered by the shopping malls of Mangaluru. It was found that, attributes like facilities, promotional strategies, pricing strategies, process, location, reliability and additional services attract more customer flow to the malls and provide maximum satisfaction to the customers in shopping malls. Further the demographic elements such as educational level, monthly income, and association with the malls have significant impact on the customer satisfaction. This has resulted in repeated purchase, loyalty, customer retention behavior in word of mouth promotional tool, and profitability to the shopping malls. The results will help shopping malls owners to better serve new generations of customers and offer the experiences they expect in order to sustain in this competitive market. Today shopping malls are in a mode of transformation where retailers are integrating their offerings with new digital tools like E-Commerce, social media and M-Commerce which create new opportunities and challenges not just for retailers but also for mall developers and society. Thus shopping malls have to adopt the modern approach quickly in order to stay relevant in the modern digital era.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- A.T. Kearney. (n.d). *Global retail development index*. Retrieved from <https://www.kenarney.com/global-retail-development-index>
- Akhter, S., & Equbal, I. (2012). Organized retailing in India: Challenges and opportunities. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1), 281–291.
- Amith, P. R., & Kameshvari, B. J. (2012). A study on consumer behavior of organized and unorganized retail outlets in Vadodara City. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Sciences*, 3(4), 466–474.

- Anselmsson, J. (2006). Sources of customer satisfaction with shopping malls: A comparative study of different customer segments. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 16(1), 115–138.
- Banerjee, N. (2012). A study on the attractiveness dimensions of shopping malls: An Indian perspective. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(2), 102–111.
- Das, A. (2008). *Mall management with case studies*. Taxmann Allied Services Pvt. Ltd.
- El-Adly, M. I. (2007). Shopping malls attractiveness: A segmentation approach. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 35(11), 936–950.
- Gupta, K. S., & Rangi, P. (2014). *Research methodology methods, tools and techniques*. Kalyani Publishers.
- IBEF. (2019). *Retail industry in India*. Retrieved from <https://www.ibef.org/industry/retail-india.aspx>
- India Retailing. (2016, May 19). Evolution of shopping malls in India. Retrieved from <https://www.indiaretailing.com/2016/05/19/retail/evolution-shopping-malls-india/>
- India Retailing. (2017, November 16). Indian retail industry growth: Trends, challenges, opportunities. Retrieved from <https://www.indiaretailing.com/2017/11/16/retail/indian-retail-industry-growth-trends-challenges-opportunity/>
- India Retailing. (2019, October 9). The great Indian mall story: The rise of the shopping centre industry. Retrieved from <https://www.indiaretailing.com/2019/10/09/shopping-centre/the-great-indian-mall-story-the-rise-of-the-shopping-centre-industry/>
- Jhamb, D., & Kiran, R. (2012). Emerging trends of organized retailing in India: A shared vision of consumers and retailers' perspective. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 11(4), 481–490.
- Kim, J. W., Lee, F., & Gu Suh, Y. (2015). Satisfaction and loyalty from shopping mall experience and brand personality. *Services Marketing Quarterly*, 36(1), 62–76.
- Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2006). *Principles of marketing* (10th ed.). Pearson Education Inc.
- Madan, M., & Kumari, S. (2012). Determinants of retail customer satisfaction: A study of organised retail outlets in Delhi. *Delhi Business Review*, 13(1), 117–122.
- McKinsey & Company. (n.d.). The future of the shopping mall. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/marketing-and-sales/our-insights/the-future-of-the-shopping-mall>
- Outdoor Media Plan. (n.d.). *Malls media kit*. Retrieved from <https://outdoormediaplan.com/malls-media-kit.php>
- Realfiction Blog. (n.d.). The future of shopping malls. Retrieved from <https://blog.realfiction.com/the-future-of-shopping-malls>
- Store Discovery Optimisation. (2017). Defining customer want mall experience. Retrieved from <http://www.storediscoveryoptimisation.com/defining-customers-want-mall-experience-2017>
- Ubeja, S. K., & Bedia, D. (2012). Customer satisfaction in shopping malls: An empirical study. *Pacific Business Review International*, 5(2), 60–72.

